

ABSTRACT

Corpus-Based Perspectives on Exposition and Recapitulation in Beethoven’s Piano Sonatas

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Ludwig van Beethoven’s piano sonatas constitute a central corpus of Western classical music, reflecting a significant stylistic evolution across his compositional periods. Numerous compendia and scholarly analyses have explored these works, commonly segmenting Beethoven’s output into early, middle, and late phases based on stylistic and musically analytical criteria. In particular, his engagement with formal structures is widely regarded as a defining aspect of his compositional approach.

Despite extensive scholarly attention, comprehensive studies specifically addressing the structural relationship between exposition and recapitulation remain rare. In Beethoven’s sonatas, the differences between the two sections often go beyond what tonal resolution alone might explain (Hepokoski & Darcy, 2006; Kamien, 1976; Suurpää, 2021; Zdravić-Mihailović, 2021). Instead, these differences point to broader formal strategies, in which recapitulations frequently avoid to resolve preceding tensions (Hepokoski, 2001) or even intensify them (Chodkowski, 1971). Their treatment thus emerges as a key element in understanding Beethoven’s formal thinking (Guez, 2018; MacKay, 2021; Richards, 2013; Weber, 2000) and may serve as an indicator for significant shifts in his compositional style (Spitzer, 2017).

Based on methods established by Jiang and Müller (2011), we introduce a computational tool for visualizing structural correspondences and divergences between exposition and recapitulation sections. Utilizing automated methods for similarity detection (Figure 1a) and alignment visualization (Figure 1b), the tool highlights enlargements, abridgements, thematic congruencies, and transposition indices (Figure 1c) present in the recapitulations relative to expositions. Emphasizing the advantages of computational approaches in corpus-based research, this method provides efficient visual analyses suitable for large-scale studies. By combining automated methods with traditional musicological analysis, it enables the systematic exploration of large-scale formal processes in Beethoven’s sonatas and offers a scalable framework for addressing structural complexity across a broader repertoire.

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References

- Chodkowski, A. (1971). Zu Problemen der Reprise in der Sonatenform bei Beethoven. In *Bericht über den internationalen musikwissenschaftlichen Kongress* (pp. 362–364).
- Guez, J. (2018). The 'mono-operational' recapitulation in movements by Beethoven and Schubert. *Music Theory Spectrum*, 40(2), 227–247.
- Hepokoski, J. (2001). Back and forth from Egmont: Beethoven, Mozart, and the nonresolving recapitulation. *Nineteenth Century Music*, 25(2-3), 127–154.
- Hepokoski, J., & Darcy, W. (2006). *Elements of sonata theory: Norms, types, and deformations in the late-eighteenth-century sonata*. Oxford University Press.
- Jiang, N., & Müller, M. (2013). Automated methods for analyzing music recordings in sonata form. In *Proceedings of the international society for music information retrieval conference (ISMIR)* (pp. 595–600). Curitiba, Brazil.
- Kamien, R. (1976). Aspects of the recapitulation in Beethoven piano sonatas. *The Music Forum*, 4, 195–235.
- MacKay, J. S. (2021). The second repeat in Beethoven's sonata-form movements: Tonal, formal and motivic strategies. *Music Theory and Analysis (MTA)*, 8(1), 1–41.
- Richards, M. (2013). The anticipated tonic in Beethoven's recapitulations. *Dutch Journal of Music Theory*, 18(3), 136–154.
- Spitzer, M. (2017). The significance of recapitulation in the 'Waldstein' sonata. In *Beethoven* (pp. 363–377). Routledge.
- Suurpää, L. (2021). Structural, apparent, or parenthetical? The tonic chord in the first-movement recapitulation of Beethoven's piano sonata op. 106. *Music Theory and Analysis (MTA)*, 8(2), 340–349.
- Weber, M. (2000). Zu Beethovens invenzione: Anmerkungen insbesondere zu den Reprisen in Klaviersonaten. In A. Baldassarre, S. Kübler, & P. Müller (Eds.), *Musik denken: Ernst Lichtenhahn zur Emeritierung: 16 Beiträge seiner Schülerinnen und Schüler* (pp. 57–79). Peter Lang.
- Zdravić-Mihailović, D. (2021). Treatment of recapitulation of the first movements in the sonata form of Beethoven's string quartett op. 18. *Facta Universitatis, Series: Visual Arts and Music*, 105–115.

Figure 1. Piano sonata no. 10 in G major, op. 14 no. 2, 1st movement (Allegro). (a) SSM representation. (b) Alignment representation. (c) Transposition index.